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Abstracts

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FunGlass

Additive manufacturing of akermanite glass-ceramic scaffolds with hierarchical porosity

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Abstract

Among silicates, akermanite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{MgSi}_2\text{O}_7$) ceramics have received significant attention in the last years, in bone tissue engineering, due to their excellent in vitro bioactivity, biocompatibility, biodegradability combined with good mechanical properties. In the same field, well-established architectures, such as the many variants of three-dimensional reticulated scaffolds, have been revisited in order to achieve components with a complex pore size distribution, i.e. combining macro- and micro-porosity. We will show the successful obtainment of akermanite-based glass-ceramic scaffolds, with hierarchical porosity, by different strategies, both combining innovation in raw materials and processing. In particular, flame synthesis was adopted to form glass microsphere with akermanite stoichiometry, which were later embedded in a photocurable resin and shaped with Digital Light Processing (DLP) into 3D structures. After burn-out of the binder, glass microsphere underwent just partial sintering, by viscous flow: the substantial crystallization, in fact, impeded the full densification of struts, which featured interconnected microporosity. As an alternative, reticulated scaffolds were produced by direct ink writing of pastes based on silicone resins, filled with CaCO_3 , $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ and borax: the reaction between silica, from the oxidation of silicones (upon firing in air), and fillers yielded the desired phase, whereas water vapour release from hydrated compounds determined the foaming of struts.